

Role of FSSAI in Livestock Production in Covid -19 Pandemic Situation

Dr. Jessy Bagh

Dept. of Livestock Production & Management, CVSc & AH, OUAT

Introduction

Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI): Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI) is an autonomous statutory body established under the Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006 (FSS Act).

- Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Government of India is the administrative Ministry of FSSAI.
- Headquarters: Delhi.

Functions

- Framing of regulations to lay down the standards and guidelines of food safety.
- Granting FSSAI food safety license and certification for food businesses.
- Laying down procedure and guidelines for laboratories in food businesses.
- To provide suggestions to the government in framing the policies.
- To collect data regarding contaminants in foods products, identification of emerging risks and introduction of rapid alert system.
- Creating an information network across the country about food safety.

Promote general awareness about food safety and food standards. COVID -19 is an unprecedented emergency and grave societal threat. Public health protection is the first priority. However, governments, policy makers and the international community should also identify and try to mitigate negative impacts of pandemic and makes efforts to solution that contribute to food, security, nutrition and livelihoods. The livestock sector is a key contributor to these areas, especially for the world's most vulnerable populations.

Impacts of Covid 19 situation

- Reduces access to animal feeds
- Reduced access to inputs and services
- Reduced processing capacity
 - ✓ Compromised storage and conservation
 - ✓ Constrained informal businesses
 - ✓ Modified retailing and product demand
- Reduced consumer purchasing power
- Reduced demand and public procurement

Recommended Actions

- Measures to protect animal production and markets
- Preventive measures to ensure better quality and safety

1. Safe production practices:

- a) Controlled use of antibiotics and veterinary drugs: Residues of antibiotics and other drugs in food, as a result their use in meat producing animals pose a threat to human health and also lead to the development of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) among disease causing bacteria. Therefore, FSSAI has notified the Food Safety and Standards (Contaminants, toxins and Residues) Amendment Regulations, 2018 specifying 'Tolerance Limits' of antibiotics and other veterinary drugs in meat/meat products and poultry.
- b) Certification of animal feed/poultry feed/feed supplement: Feed is the major source of contamination with many chemical residues like Feed like pesticides, antibiotics, heavy metals etc. which contaminate meat and poultry. Hence controlling animal feed prevents the chemicals to enter food chain. As per FSS Act, animal feed does not come under the mandate of FSSAI. However, BIS has a voluntary standard for the same. All the producers of animal feed should obtain BIS certification for their feed to ensure safe meat production

2. Safety measures to be followed by food business operators

Specific hygienic and sanitary practices across entire meat food chain. All food business operator involved in meat food chain from farm to fork should follow the basic principles of safety and hygiene. Food Safety and Standards (Licensing and Registration of Food Businesses) Regulations 2011, in Part IV of Schedule 4 outlines specific Hygienic and Sanitary Practices to be followed by Food Business Operators engaged in manufacture, processing, storing and selling of meat and meat products complying quality and safety standards.

➤ **Measures to maintain processing and retail operations**

- Provide guidelines for COVID-19 control and prevention along the supply chains to protect value chain actors and their families. These guidelines should include provisions for heightened biosecurity, personal protective equipment and hygiene.
- Provide grants to increase packaging and freezing capacities. Small- and medium-sized enterprises and factories should be encouraged to produce safe products with long shelf lives.
- Organize grouped slaughtering points and support the installation of the cold chain to reduce unregulated slaughtering and improve meat inspection.
- Find alternative ways to reach children of the school feeding programmes and distribute animal-protein-rich foods to improve nutrition and smallholder incomes.

Elements of safe meat control system in FSSAI

- Identification of issues related to food quality and safety with respect to domestic and imported food products
- FSS Standards for Meat and meat products including poultry
- Development and implementation of Food Safety Management System for Licensing and registration of food business operators
- Enforcement
- Surveillance
- Consumer Awareness

Issues related to food quality and safety

A. **Safety and Hygiene Issues:** Because of being nutritionally rich and highly perishable in nature, meat and poultry products are at high risk of contamination and spoilage.

(i) Microbiological contamination

- a) Slaughtering on the floor without the possibility of hanging the carcass
- b) Carcass splitting, cutting and deboning is carried out on the same contaminated floor area
- c) Careless evisceration that spreads intestinal content onto the meat surface
- d) From worker's hands, tools, working surfaces, equipments, water, pests, packaging, different lot of meat/offal and during dressing
- e) Pathogens can also grow during production, storage or transport, if condition, particularly temperature is suitable for their growth
- f) Insufficient training, supervision, lack of awareness of the importance of hygiene measures & quality control tools (HACCP principles) leads to ineffective management systems

ii) Chemical contamination

- a) Residues of veterinary medicines, antibiotics, pesticides, heavy metals, processing aids etc.
- b) The indiscriminate use of antibiotics and veterinary drugs either for therapeutic purpose or prophylactic purpose results in drug residues in edible tissues/organs of the birds as well as eggs
- c) It may also lead to possible development of resistant strains of bacteria

(iii) Physical contamination:

This includes contamination of meat or poultry with materials such as:

- ✓ Metal such as metal from rails knife, blade, etc.
- ✓ Plastic materials
- ✓ Others such as hair, rubber, bone splinters, dust, dirt, dead insects, stone, etc.

B. Food Safety Management System (FSMS): A Food Safety Management System (FSMS) is not only an assisting tool to make sure safe practices followed within the business but a legal obligation too. ISO 22000 has been developed as an international solution for improving food safety. Rather than applying good manufacturing practices, HACCP and ISO 9001: 2000 separately, ISO 22000 :2005 is implemented to observe the synergic effect and to ensure food safety in the food supply chain. ISO 22000, also known as Food Safety Management System (FSMS), is an international auditable standard. Standard ensures a safe food supply throughout the chain and provides a framework of the internationally harmonized system for the global approach

Dos and Don'ts for Consumers

Dos

- Prefer to buy packaged and chilled/ frozen meat
- Store the meat in refrigerator ($4\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$) immediately after purchase for short term storage (2 to 4 days).
- Store the meat in deep freezer ($-18\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$) for long term storage (upto 12 months)
- Buy meat only from shops having FSSAI registration and licence
- Enquire regarding location of slaughter and ensure their hygienic standards before buying meat
- In the packaged meat and meat product, do check for manufacturing date, best before date and other declarations before buying
- Cook the meat thoroughly before consumption

➤ Keep in mind following basic points while purchasing meat and meat products:

- Freshness
- Visual appearance (colour, texture, fat content)
- Odour
- Hygienic condition of the meat outlet
- Licensing/registration status
- Personal hygiene of the retailer

Don'ts

- Do not buy meat from retail shops having unhygienic production practices
- Do not consume the meat which is smelling, slimy and greenish in colour
- Avoid buying meat from retail shops who hang the carcasses in open.

Reference

Food Safety and Standard Authority of India (FSSAI),
https://fssai.gov.in/upload/uploadfiles/files/Guidance_Note_Meat_Poultry_
Food and Agricultural Organisation of the united Nation (FAO), A Overview on Mitigating the impacts
of Covid -19 on the livestock sector.
https://youtu.be/rB_GK5T5hZY

